

Determination of Educators' Radical and Transformative Approaches on the Future of Schools

Mehmet Fırat*

Abstract

Problem Statement: Paradigm shift in education has led to questioning the future of existing schools. Different radical and transformative scenarios and points of view regarding the future of schools discussed in educational literature. However, no matter what the scenario is the role of educators in shaping the future of the schools is inevitable. However, studies which have questioned the views of educators on the future of schools from the literature are insufficient.

Purpose of the Study: The main purpose of this research is to determine the radical and transformative approaches of educators on the future of schools. For this purpose, a questionnaire consisting of two sections and 13 questions developed.

Method: Data were collected from 163 educators from 21 different countries. Views of educators on the future of schools were analyzed according to their countries, ages, genders, and technology competencies. In analysis of data, descriptive statistics (% , f, \bar{x}), Independent Samples T-test and One Way ANOVA techniques were used. SPSS 15.0 package program was used to analyze the data.

Findings and Results: According to the findings of the study, educators supported the transformative approach rather than a radical change for the future of schools. Educators also indicated that the existing schools are insufficient to train new human profile. Most of the participants supported the view of "The universal and humanistic new forms of education are to be exposed." and "The current schools are not sufficient in training of human profile that meets the needs of contemporary society."

Conclusions and Recommendations: At the end of this research it is possible to say that educators with active and leading roles can contribute to shaping the future of schools, without sentenced to probabilistic estimates. In future studies this research can be repeated with more participants from other stakeholders of educational systems like students and parents.

Keywords: Future of schools, educators, transformative approach, radical approach.

* Res. Assist. Dr., Anadolu University, Open Education Faculty, Department of Distance Education, Eskişehir, Turkey. E-mail: mfrat@anadolu.edu.tr

INTRODUCTION

As we are entering the new millennium, the unprecedentedly rapid development of information and communication technologies in the world has had a deep impact on all social, cultural, and economic structures (Toffler, 1981). The impact of these developments influencing all levels of society has also been deeply influential on the widespread educational understanding and structure of educational institutions. The fact that the effective use, production, sharing, and updating of technology particularly lay at the foundation of these developments has accelerated the impact on the learning of students and thus, the understanding of education. Now, through information technology, learners all over the world can access to content at any quantity from anywhere and anytime they desire, (Bryan, 2011). Computers, mobile phones, and the internet, which have entered nearly all aspects of our daily lives, have enhanced the access to production, sharing, and most importantly the control of information (Oçay, 2010).

Now there is a need for a human profile, which has the skills of keeping in track of constantly updated technologies, sharing and effective utilization of information in a rapid manner and also the production of information (Akkoyunlu and Kurbanoglu, 2003). This need points out the questions of the emphasis on the continuity of education and how schools addressing this should be, which are underlined by current concepts such as lifelong learning, self learning, individual learning, and e-learning. This is because current education reform strategies are either inadequate or unsuccessful (ACOT2, 2008). At this point, it is possible to say that two basic approaches concerning the future of existing schools are becoming prominent. These approaches can basically be collected under two titles as the transformative approach, which advocates the improvement of modern schools in compliance with contemporary conditions, and the radical approach, which radically questions the existence of schools in the new era (Firat, 2010; Elmore and City, 2011).

Throughout the previous century, the institutional structure and practice of education have hardly undergone any changes. Despite this, according to Schank (2008) within the fifty years to come, by means of information acquisition and computers, obtaining this information shall be easy as it has never been before and as sequencing some information consecutively shall have no value and not only the institutional structure and practice of schools but also their existence shall be directly debated. The paradigm shift in education has caused the questioning of the future of existing schools today.

The transformative approach advocates the review and restructuring of existing school systems according to contemporary conditions and needs. According to this approach, in order to address the varying needs of the information society of today, schools need a new face and identity (Zmuda, Kuklis and Kline, 2004; Glen, 2005; ACOT2, 2008). In this context, the functioning, content, and objectives of schools as the institutions shaping educated people, who are primarily among the most important dynamics of information society, should be thought over again. According to this, the school that is the need of the new society must provide to students of all ages and levels (Lipsky and Gartner, 1989) a high level of universal literacy (Miller, 1988), world citizenship (Heater, 2002), information literacy (Doyle, 1994), and self

learning opportunities (Hart, 1978) and must address all segments of society, and benefit from all organizations (Bell, 1974; Etzkowitz, 2008). Finally, new innovative approaches that can enhance student's achievement at school should be introduced (Rusten, 2003).

In a study conducted by Yelland and Lloyd (2001) interviews were held with 934 students aged between 10 and 13 on computer and video games. According to the findings obtained from the study, information and communication technology were intensively used by students and adopted as a part of their lives. According to the conclusion underlined in the study, if schools continue to ignore the impact of information and communication technologies on learning, they are face to face with being considered as Neolithic and old. Thus, it has been suggested that those who are responsible for training the next generation for the information age have to take important measures.

Apart from the transformative approach oriented at updating school structures, in other words, improving them in the new era, there are also approaches questioning the existence of schools. According to this radical approach, together with globalization, the need for schools has decreased, learning has expanded beyond the limits of schools, and become more rapid and enjoyable (Harvey, 2001). The most prominent person among those discussing this view that questions the existence of schools is undoubtedly Ivan Illich, who objects to the institutionalization of values with his book "Deschooling Society." According to this approach, for a desirable future, interpersonal proximity should be focused on rather than an inefficient and uniform education (Illich, 1971), the individual should be responsible towards nature rather than being a consumer, monopolization and commercialization of information should be prevented (Garrick and Usher, 2000), and universal and humanistic education forms should be introduced (Egan, 2008).

As it can be observed, approaches in the literature on the future of schools have a long historical background; however, it can be said that studies questioning the views of educators within the framework of the two basic approaches oriented at the restructuring of schools and questioning the existence of schools are insufficient (Firat, 2010). Thus, it is considered that this study to be conducted shall provide the literature with a significant perspective on the future of schools.

Various scenarios and perspectives can be formulated on the future of schools; however, the evident point is that educators, who are among the most apparent parties in the education system and education policies, shall have a great role in shaping the future of school irrespective of the scenario. This is because the feasible possibilities are mainly shaped by social powers surrounding the education system (Hutmacher, 2001). Particularly during this era where information technologies and globalization deeply have an impact on the understanding of education, the analysis of the approaches of educators on the future of schools has significantly become appreciated.

Objective

The objective of this study is to determine the approach of educators towards the future of schools and to analyze these approaches according to their efficiency in use

of technology, country, age, and gender variables. In line with this objective, the following are the questions for which answers have been explored in the study:

1. What are the approaches of educators on the future of schools?
2. Is there a significant relation between the approach of educators on the future of schools and efficiency in use of technology, country, age, and gender?

METHOD

A total of 163 educators have participated in this study from 21 different countries. When the field of study of educators participating in the study is examined, it can be observed that 56% study in the field of Education Technologies (teaching design, distance education, education software, information technology etc.), 16% in science and mathematics education, 10% in education sciences, and 8% in special education. The remaining portion of participants study in the fields of language education, art education, and preschool education. Among the participants 102 were from the USA, 37 from Turkey, 3 from Canada, and two from each of Italy, Greece, and Israel. One person from each of the remaining 15 countries participated in the study (Bangladesh, Chile, Czech Republic, Fiji, Germany, Iran, Ireland, Panama, Romania, Singapore, Spain, Sweden, Taiwan, England, and Uganda). Katılımcılara ilişkin diğer demografik özellikler aşağıda Tablo 1’de verilmiştir.

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of the participants

	n	%
Gender		
Female	74	45.4
Male	89	54.6
Age		
20-29	35	21.5
30-39	33	20.2
40-49	39	23.9
50-59	40	24.5
60 and over	16	9.8
Technology utilize efficiency		
very unsuccessful	10	6.1
unsuccessful	0	0
neither successful nor unsuccessful	10	6.1
successful	76	46.6
very successful	67	41.1

When the demographic characteristics of the participants are examined, it can be observed that the majority was females at 54.6% and approximately 58% of those participating in the study were 40 years old or older. Together with this, it can be observed that 87.7% of the participants consider themselves to be “successful” or “very successful” in terms of the efficiency to utilize technology. The reason for this can be that most of the educators participating in the study work in the field of information technology.

Development of the Data Collection Instrument

For the purpose of examining the views of educators on the future of schools on the basis of the transformative and radical approaches a questionnaire form was developed. The literature was utilized in the preparation of the questionnaire items. In the selection of each item, various studies conducted in the literature were taken as a reference. In Table 2 below, the source utilized for each item in its preparation has been indicated.

Table 2. Items used in the measurement instrument and their corresponding sources

No	Items used in the measurement instrument	Corresponding sources
T1	Existing schools are not insufficient in educating the human profile needed by the society of today.	(Glen, 2005; ACOT ² , 2008)
R1	Innovative approaches oriented at increasing student achievement at school should be developed.	(Patterson, 1973; Egan, 2008; Sarkan & Nemeç, 2010)
D1	Schools should develop their ability to act by creating their own institutional identity.	(Zmuda, Kuklis & Kline, 2004)
R2	School-industry-state cooperation should be enhanced.	(Garrick & Usher, 2000)
D2	The school-centered understanding of management should be promoted.	(Cohen, 1989; Brown, 1990; Murphy & Beck, 1995)
D3	The monopolization and commercialization of information through schools should be prevented.	(Etzkowitz, 2008)
D4	New universal and humanistic forms of education should be introduced.	(Moles, 1996; Rusten, 2003)
R3	Extensive communication networks should be developed instead of schools.	(Harasim, Hiltz, Teles & Turoff, 1995; Smith, 2001)
R4	Together with globalization, as learning has extended beyond the limits of schools and become more rapid and enjoyable, there is no need left for schools.	(Illich, 1971; Bentley, 1998; Harvey, 2001; Sandlin, Schultz & Burdick, 2010)

T: impartial, R: radical, D: transformative

For the sake of validity of scope and appearance the questionnaire form prepared by utilizing the literature was presented to three academicians that are experts in the field of education for their evaluations and especially the articulation of the items was reinforced in line with the expert opinions. Principal Components Analysis, which is a factor analysis technique, was utilized in order to test and specify the components, for which 8 items were collected together, except the first item (T1) of the questionnaire questioning the current states of the schools. Thus, research sample was utilized in line with the Principal Components Analysis. The Principal Components Analysis is a technique used to express the variance structure of the original variables through fewer new variables (Jolliffe, 1986).

It was stated that in the literature in the determination of the components the factor loads of the items, which vary between 0.30 and 0.45, could be used as lower cut-off points (Büyüköztürk, 2007). In this study 0.40 factor load value was taken as a basis as a lower cut-off point. Rotated Principal Components Matrix shown in Table 3 below.

Table 3. Principal components matrix

No	Items	Components	
		1	2
D3	The monopolization and commercialization of information through schools should be prevented.	.730	-.041
D1	Schools should develop their ability to act by creating their own institutional identity.	.706	.318
D2	The school-centered understanding of management should be promoted.	.630	.012
D4	New universal and humanistic forms of education should be introduced.	.403	.047
R3	Extensive communication networks should be developed instead of schools.	.083	.810
R4	Together with globalization, as learning has extended beyond the limits of schools and become more rapid and enjoyable, there is no need left for schools.	-.059	.799
R1	Innovative approaches oriented at increasing student achievement at school should be developed.	.378	.461
R2	School-industry-state cooperation should be enhanced.	.298	.401

As can be seen in Table 3 items derived from literature collected under two factors after Principal Components Analysis. Items supporting the transformative approach (T1, T2, T3, and T4) and items supporting the radical approach (R1, R2, R3, and R4) were collected under different factors. This finding indicates that the items that are formed by utilizing the literature represent the prospective components. The factor loads of the items that are collected under the first component vary between .403 and .730 and the factor loads of the items that are collected under the second component vary between .401 and .810. This could be accepted as an indicator of the questionnaire measuring well the structure, which is aimed to be measured.

As a result of the validity and reliability studies of the questionnaire items, a questionnaire consisting of 2 sections and 13 questions was obtained. In the first section of the questionnaire there are 4 items questioning the demographic characteristics of the educators and in the second section there are 9 items questioning their approaches concerning the future of the schools.

Data Collection

Support was received from an educator graduated from the Department of Teaching English in the translation of the questionnaire form that was finalized with the assistance of an expert opinion. The finalized questionnaire form was transferred to Google Documents Application and then transformed into an online questionnaire that may be easily accessed by the participants. The questionnaire form was added to the e-mail lists of ITFORUM (Information Technology Forum), IFETS (International Forum of Educational Technology and Society), and EDTECH (Educational Technology) as a discussion issue. After the list administrator's approval, the study was made accessible to the list members. In this way the list members participated in

the study by clicking the questionnaire link whenever they wished. The questionnaire form was added in the same manner to the e-mail lists of the groups called “Teachers Information Sharing” and “Teacher Sharing Forum” and after the administrator’s approval, it was made accessible to the participants. The techniques of online questionnaire and data collection via e-mails make it easy to reach the target group and their most evident advantage is that they facilitate receiving the scientific sample and thus reinforce the external validity of the study (Andrews, Nonnecke and Preece, 2003).

Data Analysis

In this study descriptive statistics such as percentage (%), frequency (f), and average (\bar{X}), two samples of t-test, and One-Way ANOVA test were utilized in the data collected with 13 five-point Likert type items. In the analysis of data SPSS 15.0 package program was used.

FINDINGS

In parallel with the purpose of the research, findings obtained as a result of data analysis were given under the headings of “Examining Educators’ approaches on the future of schools” and “Examining the approaches in terms of independent variables.”

Educators’ approaches on the future of schools

In the second section of the questionnaire the first item as “Existing schools are not insufficient in educating the human profile needed by the society of today” emphasizes that the schools are insufficient to meet the need of new human profile and does not represent a view regarding the future of the schools. Among the other 8 items, 4 items represent the transformative approach arguing for the reconsideration and constitution of the existing school systems in accordance with today’s needs and conditions and the other 4 items represent the radical approach questioning radically the presence of the schools in the new era. Total scores and average values of these 9 items assessed by the educators are given in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. Total scores of the items

When the total scores of the items are examined, it can be observed that the 7th item (New universal and humanistic forms of education should be introduced) received the highest score advocating the reconsideration and constitution of the existing school systems in accordance with today's needs and conditions. The 9th item (Together with globalization, as learning has extended beyond the limits of schools and become more rapid and enjoyable, there is no need left for school) received the lowest score concerning the radical approach. Total score percentages of the items pertaining to radical and transformative approaches are given in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2. Total score percentages

When the total score percentages of the items pertaining to radical and transformative approaches on the future of schools are examined, it can be observed that the transformative approach received 56% but radical approach received 44% of all scores. Total score averages of the items representing the two approaches on the future of schools were $\bar{X}=2.98$ for the radical view and $\bar{X}=3.81$ for the transformative view. In that case it can be said that the educators remained impartial for the radical approach on the future of schools ($\bar{X}=2.98$), but supported the transformative approach ($\bar{X}=3.81$).

Examining the approaches on the future of the schools in terms of independent variables

Educators' views on the future of schools were examined in terms of their countries, ages, genders, and their abilities in the use of technology. Thus, independent two samples of t-test and One-Way ANOVA test were utilized. First, normal distribution as a parametric test condition was examined. In order to test the normality of collected data Kolmogorow-Smirnow test used. The results of the test are given below in Table 4.

Table 4. Kolmogorov-Smirnow test results

	N	\bar{X}	SS	Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z	p
Future of Schools	163	3,47	,58	1,25	.085

According to the result of Kolmogorov-Smirnov normality test, it was observed that educators' scores on the future of schools demonstrated a normal distribution [$D_{(163)} = 1.25$, $p = .085 > 0.05$]. This finding indicates that the condition of normal distribution is provided for the application of the parametric tests to the data obtained.

As a result of the independent samples t-test and One-Way ANOVA test, educators' views on the future of schools in consideration of their demographic characteristics demonstrated some significant differences only in terms of their countries. These differences occurred between North American (Canada and the USA) and European countries, which both provided the highest participation in the research. Results of the t-test are given below in Table 5.

Table 5. Independent samples t-test results

Approaches	Groups	N	\bar{X}	SS	SD	t	p
Radical Approach	European	50	4,3800	,56749	153	2.171	,031
	North American	10	4,0857	1,11902	5		
Transformative Approach	European	50	4,1150	,81786	153	2.818	,005
	North American	10	3,7881	,59624	5		

First of all, it was observed that in Levene F test variances were homogeneous for all groups ($p > .05$). So it is possible to say that the result that will be obtained from the t-test is significant. As a result of the independent two samples of the t-test, a significant difference was observed for only the "transformative approach" among the participants' views on the future of schools according to their countries [$t_{(155)} = 2.81$, $p < .05$]. When the average scores for the educators' views on the future of schools are examined, it can be observed that the Europeans ($\bar{X} = 4,11$) favor the transformative approach rather than the Americans and the Canadians ($\bar{X} = 3,78$) at a significant level ($p < .01$). In addition, as a result of the independent two samples of the t-test, it is seen that according to their countries the participants demonstrate a significant difference in terms of efficiency in the use of technology [$t_{(155)} = 2.17$, $p < .05$]. Accordingly, European educators regard themselves as more efficient than the North American educators on the utilization of technology ($4.38 > \bar{X} = 4.08$).

DISCUSSION

In the study it can be observed that the educators favor significantly the transformative approach and the view of the inefficiency of the existing schools to train the needed human profile more than expected. In this connection, it is seen that the educators favor the conservative approach rather than the radical change on the future of schools. Besides, it is possible to say that the educators consider existing schools to be insufficient to train the new human profile needed. This phenomenon is capable of supporting Yelland and Lloyd's (2001) view of accepting schools to be obsolescent over time (Due to the proliferation of information and communication technologies).

When the educators' views on the future of the schools are examined in terms of their demographic characteristics, there appear significant differences only in consideration of their countries regarding the efficiency in the utilization of technology and the transformative approach. Accordingly, European educators support significantly the transformative approach on the future of the schools more than their American and Canadian counterparts. This transatlantic difference may be due to Europe's resistance to more conservative and radical changes; however, most schools in Europe are state-based (Etzkowitz, Webster, Gebhardt and Terra, 2000) and this could be the reason for the preference of the transformation shaped by new needs rather than the radical change.

When the responses concerning how the educators consider themselves for the efficiency in the utilization of technology are examined, it appears that the American and Canadian educators consider themselves to be less efficient in the use of technology than the counterparts in Europe. This may be due to the European participants' lower level of age averages or American and Canadian educators' unwillingness to control technology unlike their counterparts in Europe. According to Vallance and Towndrow (2007), the educators in North America allow themselves to be controlled by technology (consciously or unconsciously).

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

In this study an attempt was made to determine the educators' approaches on the future of schools. To this end, a data collection instrument was prepared by the researcher and data were collected from 163 educators in 21 countries on a voluntary basis. Educators' approaches on the future of schools were examined from the data obtained in terms of various variables.

When the results obtained from the research are observed, the item of

“New universal and humanistic education systems should be introduced” becomes the most supported view of the educators whereas it is determined that the approach of “Together with globalization, as learning has extended beyond the limits of schools and become more rapid and enjoyable, there is no need left for school” becomes the least supported view. In parallel with these results, it can be said that educators remain impartial for the radical approach on the future of schools but often support the transformative approach.

When the position of the results obtained from the research within practical implementation is observed, it is possible to say that two conditions become prominent. First, as the probability of how the schools will be in future is shaped by the current perspectives of the parties (Hutmacher, 2001), the institution's improvement and refinement activities on vision and mission may be performed by all parties. So it may be possible to have a part in shaping the future without being dependent on probabilistic predictions concerning the future of schools. The second condition is that educators may play an active and leading role in developing the innovative approaches regarding the future of the schools. In connection with this, it is possible to summarize the role of technology in shaping tomorrow's schools and the exact time to utilize from it by way of the citation of Means and Olson (1994) below.

“The power of technology will emerge when integrated with the serious education reforms; however, schools need to review their own missions and structures starting from the student needs and instructional principles before they discuss how technology will be set to work.” (Means and Olson, 1994, p. 116).

In the studies that shall be performed in future, above all more significant results may be achieved by repeating this research with more target groups because the large majority of the research participants come from the same countries. For example in this research there are very few participants from Western Europe. In addition, as the other direct parties of the education systems students, managers, and the families' views on the future of schools may be examined in parallel with this research.

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Eğitimcilerin Okulların Geleceğine İlişkin Radikal ve Dönüştürücü Yaklaşımlarının Belirlenmesi

Özet

Problem Durumu: Geçtiğimiz yüzyıl boyunca eğitimin kurumsal yapısı ve pratiği neredeyse hiç değişime uğramamıştır. Ancak son yirmi yıl içerisinde bilgi edinme ve bilişim teknolojileriyle bilgiye hakim olma hiç olmadığı kadar kolaylaşmıştır. Bu nedenle toplumun ihtiyaç duyduğu yeni insan profilini yetiştirmek için eğitim ve öğretimde yeni yaklaşımlara ihtiyaç duyulmaktadır.

Artık sürekli güncellenen teknolojileri takip edebilen, bilgi üretiminin yanında bilginin hızlı bir şekilde paylaşılması ve etkili kullanılması becerilerine sahip insan profiline ihtiyaç duyulmaktadır. Toplumun ihtiyaç duyduğu insan profilini yetiştirmek için mevcut eğitim anlayışı ve eğitim sistemleri bilişim teknolojilerinin eğitime entegrasyonu temelinde önemli bir dönüşüm geçirmektedir. Eğitimdeki paradigma değişimi günümüzdeki mevcut okulların geleceğinin sorgulanmasına da neden olmuştur.

Mevcut okulların geleceğiyle ilgili iki temel yaklaşımın ön plana çıktığını söylemek mümkündür. Bu yaklaşımlar; modern okulların günün koşullarına uygun olarak iyileştirilmesini savunan dönüştürücü yaklaşım ve yeni dönemde okulun varlığını temelden sorgulayan radikal yaklaşımdır.

Okulların geleceğine ilişkin farklı senaryolar ve bakış açıları oluşturulabilir. Ancak hangi senaryo olursa olsun okulların geleceğinin şekillendirilmesinde eğitimcilerin rolü kaçınılmazdır. Buna rağmen eğitimcilerin görüşlerini sorgulayan çalışmalar alanyazında yetersizdir. Bu nedenle gerçekleştirilen bu araştırmanın alanyazına okulların geleceğine yönelik önemli bir bakış açısı sağlayacağı düşünülmektedir.

Okulların gelecekte nasıl olacakları olasılıkları tarafların şimdiki bakış açıları tarafından şekillendiğinden dolayı eğitimciler, yöneticiler, öğrenciler ve aileler dahil tüm taraflarla vizyon ve misyon geliştirme, eğitsel uygulamalarda bilişim teknolojilerden faydalanma ve buna yönelik pratik uygulamaların ilerletme çalışmalarının gerçekleştirilmesi gerektiği düşünülmektedir.

Araştırmanın Amacı: Bu çalışmanın amacı eğitimcilerin okulların geleceğine ilişkin yaklaşımlarını belirlemek ve bu yaklaşımları teknoloji kullanım yeterlilikleri, ülke, yaş ve cinsiyet değişkenlerine göre incelemektir. Bu amaç doğrultusunda araştırmada cevabı aranan sorular şunlardır:

- 1) Eğitimcilerin okulların geleceğine ilişkin yaklaşımları nelerdir?
- 2) Eğitimcilerin okulların geleceğine ilişkin yaklaşımları ile teknoloji kullanım yeterlilikleri, ülke, yaş ve cinsiyetleri arasında anlamlı bir ilişki var mıdır?

Yöntem: Araştırmanın genel amacı doğrultusunda araştırmacılar tarafından alanyazındaki araştırmalardan yararlanılarak bir anket formu geliştirilmiştir. Anket maddelerinin geçerlik ve güvenilirlik çalışmaları sonucunda 2 bölüm ve 13 sorudan oluşan bir anket elde edilmiştir. Anketin birinci bölümünde eğitimcilerin demografik özelliklerini sorgulayan 4 madde, ikinci bölümünde ise okulların geleceğine ilişkin yaklaşımlarını sorgulayan 9 madde bulunmaktadır.

Araştırma kapsamında 21 farklı ülkeden 163 eğitimciden veri toplanmıştır. Katılımcıların 102'si ABD'den 37'si Türkiye'den, 3'ü Kanada'dan, ikişer tanesi İtalya, Yunanistan ve İsrail'den araştırmaya katılmışlardır. Kalan 15 ülkeden (Bangladeş, Şili, Çek Cumhuriyeti, Fiji, Almanya, İran, İrlanda, Panama, Romanya, Singapur, İspanya, İsveç, Tayvan, İngiltere ve Uganda) ise birer kişi araştırmaya katılmıştır.

Katılımcıların demografik özelliklerine bakıldığında % 54.6'sının bayan olduğu, % 58'inin 40 yaş ve üzerinde olduğu görülmektedir. Bununla birlikte katılımcıların % 87.7'sinin teknoloji kullanım yerlilikleri açısından kendilerini "başarılı" veya "çok başarılı" olarak gördükleri görülmektedir.

Eğitimcilerin okulların geleceğine ilişkin görüşleri ülkeleri, yaşları, cinsiyetleri ve teknoloji kullanım yeterliliklerine göre analiz edilmiştir. Verilerin analizinde betimsel istatistikler (% , f, \bar{x}), Bağımsız Örneklem T-testi ve Tek Yönlü ANOVA tekniklerinden yararlanılmıştır.

Bulgular: Okulların geleceğine ilişkin alanyazından elde edilen anket maddelerin aldığı toplam puanlara bakıldığında en yüksek puanı okul sistemlerinin günün koşullarına ve ihtiyaçlarına göre tekrar gözden geçirilmesi ve yapılandırılmasını savunan dönüştürücü yaklaşıma ait "Evrensel ve insancıl yeni eğitim biçimleri ortaya çıkarılmalıdır." Maddesinin aldığı görülmüştür. En düşük puanı ise radikal yaklaşıma ait "Küreselleşme ile birlikte öğrenme okul sınırlarının dışına taşıdığı, daha hızlı ve keyifli hale geldiği için okula gerek kalmamıştır." maddesinin aldığı görülmüştür. Ayrıca maddelerin toplam puan yüzdelere bakıldığında dönüştürücü yaklaşımın tüm puanların % 56'sını, radikal yaklaşımın ise % 44'ünü aldığı görülmüştür.

Eğitimcilerin okulların geleceğine ilişkin görüşleri demografik özellikleri açısından incelendiğinde ülkeleri açısından teknoloji kullanım yeterliliği ve dönüştürücü yaklaşım ile ilgili anlamlı farklılıklar ortaya çıkmıştır. Buna göre Avrupalı eğitimcilerin okulların geleceğine ilişkin dönüştürücü yaklaşımı ABD ve Kanadalı eğitimcilerden anlamlı bir şekilde daha fazla desteklemiştir. Ayrıca ABD ve Kanadalı eğitimcilerin kendilerini teknoloji kullanımında Avrupalı eğitimcilerden daha yetersiz gördükleri ortaya çıkmıştır. Araştırmadan bulgulara bakıldığında eğitimcilerin okulların geleceğine ilişkin radikal yaklaşıma tarafsız kaldıkları ($\bar{X}=2.98$), dönüştürücü yaklaşımı ise destekledikleri ($\bar{X}=3.81$) söylenebilir.

Sonuç ve Öneriler: Araştırmadan elde edilen bulgulara göre akademisyenlerin okulların geleceğine ilişkin radikal bir kökten değişimden çok dönüştürücü yaklaşımdan yana oldukları ve mevcut okul sistemlerinin ihtiyaç duyulan yeni insan profilini yetiştirmede yetersiz olduğunu savundukları görülmüştür.

Gelecekte yapılacak araştırmalarda daha fazla hedef kitle ile bu araştırma tekrarlanabileceği gibi eğitim sistemlerinin diğer doğrudan tarafları olan öğrenciler, yöneticiler ve ailelerin okulların geleceğine ilişkin görüşleri de sorgulanabilir. Böylece daha anlamlı sonuçlara ulaşılabilir. Olasılıklı kestirimlere bağlı kalmadan eğitimciler aktif ve öncü rolleriyle okulların geleceğinin şekillenmesine katkı sağlayabilirler.

Anahtar Sözcükler: Okulların geleceği, eğitimciler, dönüştürücü yaklaşım, radikal yaklaşım.